

UPDATE ON THE PROPOSED CHANGES IN THE FCC RULES
GOVERNING ISM EQUIPMENT

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ABSTRACT

In 1976, the Federal Communications Commission proposed an overall revision of Part 18 of its rules governing the interference potential of Industrial, Scientific & Medical (ISM) equipment. International events starting with the World Administrative Radio Conference of 1979 (WARC-79) have overshadowed this proceeding making it imperative for U.S. communication and ISM manufacturers and users to follow these developments. This paper discusses the present FCC Rules governing ISM equipment, the FCC proposal to revise Part 18, the status of effort to adopt international requirements for such equipment, and finally the importance of such recommendations to U.S. ISM and communication users and manufacturers.

BACKGROUND

FCC Rules Part 18

The Federal Communications Commission was established by the Communications Act of 1934 and given the responsibility to oversee use of the radio spectrum and ensure the protection of radio communications against interference. The Commission carries out this responsibility through establishment of regulations as deemed necessary. The FCC some 30 years ago promulgated rules in Part 18 to control interference from Industrial Scientific and Medical (ISM) equipment (1). The Part 18 Rules as they stand today are fundamentally the same as when originally adopted (2).

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The term Industrial, Scientific and Medical Equipment refers to equipment that utilizes radio frequency (RF) energy to perform work, exclusive of equipment used for communication purposes. The work may involve heating a material, ionizing a gas, causing mechanical vibrations or producing other physical, chemical or biological effects.

Part 18 divides ISM equipment into several categories: ultrasonic, industrial heating, RF stabilized arc welders, miscellaneous equipment and induction cooking ranges. Some examples of this equipment are dielectric heaters used for heating, drying, molding and bonding plastics for production of inexpensive toys and other goods and induction heaters used for quick drying glue in the production of plywood. Perhaps the most well known ISM equipment is the domestic microwave oven, classified as miscellaneous ISM equipment.

The common characteristic of most ISM equipment is utilization of a high power radio frequency oscillator. If an antenna were to be connected to the output of the oscillator it would be a radio transmitter. In practice, the equipment is designed to apply RF energy to the material to be heated or worked on. Nevertheless, a portion of the energy escapes from the machine and is capable of causing harmful interference to radio communications unless some precautions are taken in the design and maintenance of the machine.

Under the rules in Part 18, certain frequencies are allocated both nationally and internationally for ISM equipment, where unlimited radiation is permitted for such equipment. The frequencies are listed in Table 1, below.

TABLE I

<u>ISM FREQUENCY</u>	<u>TOLERANCE</u>
13.56 MHz	+ 6.78 kHz
27.12 MHz	+ 160.0 kHz
40.68 MHz	+ 20.0 kHz
915. MHz	+ 13.0 MHz
2450. MHz	+ 50.0 MHz
5800. MHz	+ 75.0 MHz
24125. MHz	+125.0 MHz

Communications equipment which operates in these ISM bands is secondary to ISM equipment.

Emissions outside the ISM bands are subject to specific limits as set forth in Part 18. The two most frequently used limits are 10 $\mu\text{V}/\text{m}$ at 1 mile for industrial heating equipment and 25 $\mu\text{V}/\text{m}$ at 1000 feet for medical diathermy and miscellaneous equipment. In some instances a relaxation is permitted for equipment that generates RF energy above 500 watts. These limits apply to harmonic and spurious emissions from equipment operating within an ISM band, as well as all emissions from equipment designed to operate outside the ISM bands. The specific limits that apply to each category of equipment are given in reference (3) and in Part 18.

Part 18 requires ISM equipment to be tested to determine compliance with the emissions limits and to be authorized in accordance with certain administrative procedures called type approval and certification. Details on what these procedures require are given in reference (1) and Parts 2 and 18 of the FCC Rules.

Regulations set forth in Part 2, Subpart I proscribe the marketing of such equipment before it has been authorized as required. These rules exempt certain ISM equipment from the marketing restrictions, provided it is authorized prior to being put in use.

FCC DOCKET 20718

In the fall of 1978 the FCC proposed a comprehensive revision of the rules in Part 18 in FCC Docket 20718. The proposal was issued in two parts. New technical limits and administrative provisions were contained in the Notice of Proposed Rule Making (NPRM) (4). Detailed measurement procedures were published shortly thereafter in a Second Notice of Proposed Rule Making (5).

The Commission explained that there are a number of important reasons for revising Part 18, chief among which are: ISM equipment is considered to be the largest source of manmade radio noise; the present limits are out of line with limits for other types of equipment and are inadequate to protect future communication needs; requests for tighter limits had been made by other U.S. Government agencies; the present specifications are much more liberal than those imposed by other countries; and, there are several administrative difficulties with the present rules. A complete explanation is given in the NPRM and additional background can be found in reference (6).

The proposed emissions limits closely paralleled those recommended by the International Special Committee on Radio Interference in C.I.S.P.R. Publication 11 (7). CISPR is an international organization which has adopted a number of recommendations for controlling interference

from electrical equipment. Its recommendations are not mandatory, but are often adopted as national law by the participating countries. The present CISPR Publication 11 limits are shown in Table II, below.

TABLE II-ISM LIMITS RECOMMENDED BY CISPR

Frequency range (MHz)	On test site, at a distance from the equipment of		Not on a test site, at a distance of		
	30 m ($\mu\text{V}/\text{m}$)	100 m ($\mu\text{V}/\text{m}$)	30 m from the boundary of users' premises ($\mu\text{V}/\text{m}$)	100 m ($\mu\text{V}/\text{m}$)	300 m from the equip- ment ($\mu\text{V}/\text{m}$)
0.15 to 0.285	-	50	-	50	50
0.285 to 0.49	-	250	-	250	250
0.49 to 1.605	-	50	-	50	50
1.605 to 3.95	-	250	-	250	250
3.95 to 30	-	50	-	50	50
30 to 470	30 in TV bands 500 outside these bands	-	30* 500**	-	-
470 to 1000	100 in TV bands; 500 out- side these bands	-	100* 500**	-	200

* Compliance with these limits is required only for the TV channels in use at any time at the site.

**Limits for use outside the TV channels in use at the time at the site.

NOTE: The recommended CISPR limit for radiation from microwave equipment used for heating and medical therapy for all frequencies 1 GHz to 18 GHz is 57dB (pw)-ERP referred to a halfwave dipole.

Comments submitted by most U.S. manufacturers and users of ISM equipment generally opposed the proposal, particularly with regard to the stricter emissions limits. They argued that the reported number of cases of ISM interference is low and does not justify a tightening of the limits.

Further action in Docket 20718 was delayed because of other pressing matters, except to adopt special provisions for induction cooking ranges (8). Meanwhile, attention turned to developments that have taken place internationally concerning ISM equipment. As will be elaborated later in this paper, the outcome of these events may ultimately influence what requirements are placed on ISM equipment in the United States.

INTERNATIONAL ACTIVITY

In 1979 the World Administrative Radio Conference (WARC-79) adopted Resolution No. 63, requesting the International Radio Consultative Committee (CCIR) to prepare, in collaboration with the CISPR, as soon as possible, a Recommendation on limits to be imposed on ISM equipment both inside and outside the ISM bands. The resolution stemmed from a decision to add several new ISM frequencies, and reflected concern by some administrations about potential ISM interference to modern and future communications systems, and particularly to aeronautical navigation equipment.

In response to the WARC Resolution, CCIR Study Group 1 drafted a Study Program AT/1 and established an Interim Working Party 1/4, under the Chairmanship of Professor R. G. Struzak of Poland, to prepare the requested Recommendation. Approximately 15 countries have elected to participate, as well as representatives of 2 ISM manufacturers groups and representatives from the CISPR.

The Chairman of IWP 1/4 initiated the work of the committee in the spring of 1981 by distributing a questionnaire to gather basic information on usage of ISM equipment in each country, the amount of interference that is being experienced and viewpoints on the acceptability of the CISPR Publication 11 limits. In the United States comments were solicited from all interested parties (9). Based upon the various inputs received, a U.S.A. response was prepared and submitted to the Chairman of the IWP (10).

The results of the Chairman's survey were quite interesting. The interference statistics worldwide show that the ISM interference is small in comparison with other radio frequency sources such as CB radio and home appliances. However, many members emphasize that the interference statistics alone do not give the complete picture. The frequency of ISM equipment often shifts while performing its intended function (e.g. heating), thus making it difficult to trace ISM

interference. It is therefore believed that most ISM interference goes unreported.

The positions put forward by the IWP 1/4 members relative to the CISPR limits were sharply divergent. Manufacturers stated that the CISPR limits are far more stringent than necessary. They assert that most administrations recognize this as evidenced by the fact that they do not actively enforce the CISPR limit. On the other hand, some countries stated that the CISPR limits do not provide adequate interference protection in certain bands. There were also those who took a middle ground, stating that they are satisfied with the CISPR limits as they now stand.

From subsequent discussions of the results of the initial survey, it has become clear that the CISPR limits, at least in their present form, should not be accepted by CCIR as an international recommendation for ISM equipment.

Development of limits. As indicated earlier, members of the CISPR have been participating in the IWP 1/4 activity. As a result of the concern in the IWP about the propriety of the CISPR limits, several proposals for revision of the CISPR limits have been submitted in the CISPR and will be considered at the CISPR Working Group meetings scheduled to take place in June, 1983 in Kristiansand, Norway. It is hoped that through a coordinated effort, CCIR and CISPR will arrive at mutually agreeable ISM limits.

The scope and complexity of the technical issues and potential economic impact make the task of developing ISM limits a formidable one. Severe ISM limits would result in substantial increases in the costs of ISM equipment, which would inevitably be passed along to consumers of products made with such equipment. Of greater concern is that some production line applications, where a high degree of shielding is not possible, might be ruled out altogether and alternative production techniques may not be available. Surely this would not be desirable.

By the same token it is necessary to ensure that radio communications are adequately protected against interference. However, the significance of ISM limits towards accomplishing this goal is unclear. The present U.S.A. limits are far more lax than in other countries, yet the amount of reported ISM interference is low in the U.S.A. and abroad. While several factors may be the cause of this, it appears that a better understanding is needed of the interference interaction between ISM equipment and communication systems and the criteria used to establish limits.

Traditional approaches to interference analysis, often based upon an assumption of worst case conditions, must be reexamined. One new concept that is being investigated is to allow an adjustment of the limit based on the probability that interference will occur (11). Another is to provide some relaxation of the limit due to the non stable nature of ISM emissions -- the frequencies of the emissions from certain types of

ISM equipment shift as conditions of the load change during the work cycle. The interference signal may thus be in the pass band of a potential victim receiver only momentarily.

The frequency range over which limits are required is not explicit in the WARC-79 Resolution 63, but the implication is that CCIR should recommend limits up to 300 GHz. This will be a monumental task. Little has been done before to analyze ISM interference above 1 GHz and almost no relevant information is available above 18 GHz. There is also the question of how to address limits within the ISM bands, since the resolution gives no specific guidance on what level of protection is to be given communication services in the ISM bands that up until now have operated on a secondary basis.

Compliance with ISM limits by equipment manufacturers is still only one important factor in controlling ISM interference. Often when interference occurs the problem can be traced to the ISM user removing panels on the cabinet, or failing to replace screws after servicing the equipment, that are necessary to provide the required shielding. Thus the responsibility for compliance with emissions limits must rest partially with the user, who must ensure that the equipment is properly maintained.

Time element: The WARC Resolution 63 requests a Recommendation as soon as possible. The Chairman of IWP 1/4 has indicated that he intends for the IWP 1/4 to prepare its final Recommendation in 1984, so that there is sufficient lead time for it to be considered at the CCIR Study Group 1 meetings in 1986. After June, 1983, further work of the IWP is to be carried on by correspondence.

U.S.A. position: U.S.A. inputs to the IWP have been coordinated with as many interested parties as possible in order to present a balanced U.S.A. viewpoint among ISM equipment manufacturers and users, communications users and government regulators. This is being accomplished primarily through the American National Standards Institute Committee C63, with participation by representatives from the IEEE High Frequency Heating Committee and the National Telecommunications and Information Administration (representing Government users of the spectrum). Final inputs are coordinated through the U.S. National Committee of CCIR Study Group 1.

In order to help familiarize foreign administrations with the U.S.A. approach to regulation of ISM interference, the authors have published a paper and distributed copies to the members of IWP 1/4 (12).

Considerable effort will be required to review existing proposals on limits and develop well reasoned U.S.A. alternatives. The amount of resources that the FCC can devote to the IWP and CISPR activity is limited. Participation

by industry and communication users is strongly encouraged particularly in view of the potential impact as discussed below.

An Ad Hoc Committee has been established, under the auspices of the American National Standards Institute Committee C63, to formulate a U.S.A. position on limits. The work of this committee will continue while the discussions on ISM limits in the CISPR and IWP 1/4 proceed. Anyone wishing to participate may contact either of the authors.

Potential impact: The action taken at WARC-79 and ensuing CCIR activity is significant because the ultimate CCIR Recommendation may be considered at some later international radio conference, and at that time specific ISM limits may be incorporated in the International Telecommunications Union (ITU) Radio Regulations. It would be incumbent upon each signatory to implement these limits in their national regulations. In the United States the limits could be made mandatory by adopting new FCC regulations through the usual notice and comment rulemaking process.

The potential for this sequence of events coming to pass should not be treated lightly. Nor should U.S. manufacturers assume that past lax enforcement of ISM limits by some foreign administrations may continue. Requirements in the International Radio Regulations would put the situation in a completely new light. Therefore we cannot overemphasize the need for all interested parties to put forward their views.

POSSIBLE FUTURE ACTION IN DOCKET 20718

The proposal in Docket 20718 may take several steps to finalize. First, the question of limits will probably be held in abeyance pending the outcome of the developments in CCIR and CISPR towards a Recommendation on ISM limits. Second, a new proposal for clarifying the present administrative requirements in Part 18 will have to be initiated in the very near future. Third, a proposal controlling interference from certain new consumer type ISM equipment may be required if the effort for voluntary EMI standards does not come to successful completion.

One subject to be addressed separately in the near future is radio frequency lighting. Several types of energy efficient radio frequency lighting sources are reaching final stages of development and will soon be ready to be introduced into the marketplace in large quantities. Early indications are that unless emissions are adequately controlled the potential for interference can be great. Action looking towards possible regulations for these devices is expected in the summer of 1983.

The Commission recently received a request from Hewlett Packard Co. to exempt medical (ultrasonic) equipment from Part 18. This

matter will likely also be handled in an individual proceeding.

We expect that action will be taken in the near future to delete the requirement to file Form 724 which advises the Commission of the location of each ISM equipment. This form, at one time used to help trace ISM interferences, is no longer useful because it is now easier to find the interference by using modern direction finding equipment.

Lastly, an acceptable procedure must be found for measuring microwave oven emissions using modern equipment. The current procedure calls for use of field intensity meters of a type that are no longer made. Since the FCC Laboratory has the necessary equipment and performs the required measurements, the situation has not caused industry severe hardship. However, due to limited resources this situation may not continue indefinitely.

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